

Supporting Information: Tailored Coupled Cluster Theory in Varying Correlation Regimes

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1 Orbitals

Figure 1: HF orbitals of the P4 model in the DZP basis set with corresponding symmetry labels. The orbitals were generated by the PySCF program package [1] and plotted with VMD [2].

Figure 2: HF orbitals of the H8 model in the DZ basis set with corresponding symmetry labels. The orbitals were generated by the PySCF program package [1] and plotted with VMD [2].

2 Potential Energy Surfaces

Figure 3: Potential energy surface for the dissociation of the P4 model. The energies were calculated by TCCSD(2,2), CCSD and FCI, based on HF and CAS(2,2) orbitals and the reference determinants Φ_1 and Φ_2 .

Figure 4: Potential energy surface for the dissociation of the H8 model. The energies were calculated by TCCSD(2,2), CCSD and FCI, based on HF and CAS(2,2) orbitals and the reference determinants Φ_1 and Φ_2 .

Figure 5: Potential energy surface for the dissociation of the H8 model. The energies were calculated by TCCSD(8,8), CCSD and FCI, based on HF and CAS(8,8) orbitals and the reference determinants Φ_1 and Φ_2 .

2.1 T_1 and D_1 Diagnostics

Figure 6: T_1 and D_1 diagnostics of the H8 model for TCCSD(2,2) and CCSD based on the reference determinants Φ_1 and Φ_2 , in a HF and CAS(2,2) optimized orbital basis. The solid upper line represents the D_1 reliability threshold, while the dotted one corresponds to the T_1 reliability threshold.

Figure 7: T_1 and D_1 diagnostics of the H8 model for TCCSD(8,8) and CCSD based on the reference determinants Φ_1 and Φ_2 , in a HF and CAS(8,8) optimized orbital basis. The solid upper line represents the D_1 reliability threshold, while the dotted one corresponds to the T_1 reliability threshold.

2.2 Overlap error between CCSD and TCCSD

Figure 8: Overlap error of the H8 model between TCCSD(2,2) and CCSD based on the reference determinants Φ_1 and Φ_2 , in a HF and CAS(2,2) optimized orbital basis.

Figure 9: Overlap error of the H8 model between TCCSD(8,8) and CCSD based on the reference determinants Φ_1 and Φ_2 , in a HF and CAS(8,8) optimized orbital basis.

References

- [1] Sun, Q.; Berkelbach, T. C.; Blunt, N. S.; Booth, G. H.; Guo, S.; Li, Z.; Liu, J.; McClain, J. D.; Sayfutyarova, E. R.; Sharma, S.; Wouters, S.; Chan, G. K. PySCF: the Python-based simulations of chemistry framework. 2018.
- [2] Humphrey, W.; Dalke, A.; Schulten, K. VMD: Visual molecular dynamics. *J. Molec. Graphics* **1996**, *14*, 33–38.